

DATA NOTE

Introducing the Democratic Electoral Systems data, 1919-1945

[version 1; peer review: 2 approved, 1 approved with reservations]

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Abstract

This data note introduces an update to the widely-used Democratic Electoral Systems (DES) data that encompasses the period from 1919 to 1945. The data include 243 legislative lower house and presidential elections in 34 interwar democracies. Information on these elections falls into four categories: first and foremost, DES contains variables that capture the institutional rules that define how elections are organized. Second, the data captures the consequences of electoral rules in the form of summary statistics of electoral outcomes. Third, we include democracy classifications for four major democracy datasets so that users can choose their preferred democracy definition when working with the data. Finally, the DES dataset contains multiple identification variables that allow linking the DES data to a wide variety of other datasets. This update to the DES data is fully compatible with prior releases for the post-war period 1–3.

Plain language summary

We provide information on electoral rules between 1919 and 1945. We focus on parliamentary and presidential elections in democracies. We collect information on these rules in a dataset of 243 elections. Many rules exist. Some describe how many members a parliament has. Others determine where politicians are elected. Again others decide how individual votes a party needs to get a seat. We also describe the consequences of elections, for example, how many parties make it into parliament. There are different ways to think about what democracy is. Our dataset uses four different approaches to determine whether or not a country is a democracy so users can decide which elections to consider democratic. Our data can also be linked to many other data sources.

Open Peer Review

Approval Status

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Any reports and responses or comments on the article can be found at the end of the article.

Keywords

electoral rules, parliamentary elections, presidential elections, democracy, proportional representation, majoritarian systems

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Introduction

We are introducing an update to the widely-used Democratic Electoral Systems (DES) data that encompasses the period from 1919 to 1945. The data include 243 legislative and presidential elections in 34 interwar democracies. Information on these elections falls into four categories: first and foremost, the DES data contains variables that capture the institutional rules that define how elections are organized. Second, the data captures the consequences of electoral rules in the form of summary statistics of electoral outcomes. Third, we include democracy classifications for four major democracy datasets so that users can easily choose their preferred democracy definition when working with the data. Finally, the DES dataset contains multiple identification variables that allow linking the DES data to a wide variety of other datasets.

This release of historical DES data is fully compatible with prior releases for the post-war period¹⁻³. These DES versions have been used to analyse a broad range of questions in political science, economics, sociology, and related disciplines. Most recently, social scientists employed the data to explore outcomes such as affective polarization⁴, voting preferences in general⁵, for left and right-wing parties in particular⁶, and public participation in policy-making⁷. Prior versions of the data on electoral rules entered analyses of party systems⁸, party breakdown⁹, foreign direct investment¹⁰, ethnic coalitions¹¹, the development of legislatures in Africa¹², and elite reactions to far right challengers¹³. All these studies are highly pertinent to studying the future of democracy.¹

Although this release of the DES data covers a historical period, studies of the tumultuous interwar period might be able to teach us something about the fate of democracies today¹⁴. Studying electoral choices and reforms during the interwar period can inform debates about contemporary institutional changes. Historical party systems are relevant comparison cases for studies of the effects of party fragmentation today^{15,16}. Finally, the DES 1919–1945 release will prove a valuable resource for scholars who study the origins of electoral systems to systematically explore the diffusion of electoral rules across Europe and the Americas¹⁷.

In the following, we describe how we collected the data, how we ensure data quality, and provide a range of summary statistics that describe the data.

Materials & methods

The DES data assembles and harmonizes previously scattered and analogue sources into one data set¹⁸. Whenever possible, we rely on primary sources, such as official election returns from statistical or government agencies, and electoral laws. Edited volumes that unite case studies on electoral systems and electoral returns constitute crucial secondary sources¹⁹⁻²². We cross-referenced different sources to ensure data validity. When sources disagreed, we provide the information given by a majority of sources or contacted country experts.

Data collection relies on the experiences made in three previous rounds of post-World War II DES releases¹⁻³ and proceeded in six steps:

1. We defined the sample of elections to be included in the data. All elections must be democratic according to one of four major democracy indices: the dichotomous measure by Boix, Miller & Rosato²³, the dichotomous *Democracy and Dictatorship* (DD) classification^{24,25}, the ordinal *Polity5* index²⁶, and the continuous *Varieties of Democracy* (V-Dem) Polyarchy scale²⁷. Since the original DD classification only starts in 1946, we classified all elections in the data according to its rules.
2. We trained student research assistants (RAs) on the coding rules of the DES data^{1,3}. The training involved a theoretical overview of electoral rules, the introduction of relevant source material, and example classifications of two elections.
3. Each RA classified the same set of ten randomly selected elections. We compared RA classifications to our own classification of these elections, and provided individual performance feedback to each RA.
4. We divided the election sample between RAs according to linguistic expertise. Between ourselves and the RAs, we were able to read source material in Dutch, English, Finnish, French, German, Italian, Serbo-Croatian, Spanish, and Swedish. We encouraged RAs to contact us with questions when they were uncertain how to classify a particular variable or election. When our reading of sources could not provide an answer to unclear cases, we contacted other leading experts on electoral systems and/or particular countries to help us reach a decision.
5. We randomly re-sampled about 10% of elections and reclassified them to see if systematic errors occurred, and corrected them where necessary.
6. Specific variables are automatically created. For example, we compute the effective number of electoral parties (ENEP) at each election through an algorithm that summarises election results into the overall index. For most elections, we link DES elections to electoral results collected by the authors in a different dataset, the *Actions by Elites and Leaders* (ABEL) data¹⁶. For all other elections, we collected raw electoral results from the sources described above.
7. In a final step, we ran an automated script across the entire data to check each variable for its consistency with the coding rules, which identifies typos and other data entry mistakes. The script also ensures inter-variable consistency and thereby guarantees that two variable values do not contradict each other. For example, if the variable `legislative_type` indicates the use of proportional representation (PR) in a particular election, we checked that the variables

¹Overall, the the dataset has been cited 1385 times according to a Google Scholar query on 1 December 2023.

`elecrule` and `tier1_formula` indicate specific PR sub-types but not sub-types of any other electoral family.

The dataset comes with several identification variables that make it interoperational with other scientific and public-use datasets. Most users of the DES data are likely to link it to other country-level datasets. Thus, next to a unique variable that identifies each election (`elec_id`), the dataset provides several country-identifiers, including the country name, the country abbreviation, the Alvarez, Limongi, Cheibug & Przeworski country codes (`aclp_code`)²⁴ along with the widely-used Correlates of War (COW) country codes (`cocode`)²⁸ and the Gleditsch & Ward (GW) country IDs (`cocode2`)²⁹. Unlike identification systems of country names and different ISO country abbreviations, the COW and GW identification variables accurately trace the historical development of the international system.²

Democratic Electoral Systems, 1919–1945

To accommodate different views of democracy, we classify elections according to four different democracy definitions. Two inclusive classifications identify almost all the elections in the dataset as democratic. Boix, Miller & Rosato (BMR) only use three rules in their dichotomous democracy measure, which considers all but two Spanish parliamentary elections in 1919 and 1920 as democratic²³. Przeworski *et al.*'s DD data employs four rules to distinguish democracies from dictatorships²⁴. DD neither classifies the two Spanish elections as democratic, nor four elections in San Marino.³ The

²The two slightly differ in how they identify ancestor and successor states. For example, the COW system sees unified Germany after 1990 as a successor to Imperial/Nazi Germany before 1945, whereas GW classify unified Germany as a successor of West Germany.

³Both BMR and DD do not consider the Spanish elections as democratic because the unelected Spanish monarch could dismiss governments and revoke laws. The DD rules further dismiss the San Marino elections because the country did not experience an alternation in executive power in the period 1906–1922.

more complex V-Dem and Polity5 indices categorize 185 and 173 elections respectively as democratic. Users of our data thus have the choice to pick their preferred definition of democracy and the associated sample of elections, or to take an inclusive approach by picking all elections that have been classified as democratic by at least one democracy indicator. In the following, we present descriptive statistics based on the inclusive sample that categorizes any election as democratic that is recognized by at least one of the four democracy indicators.

Our data includes information on 213 legislative, lower-house and 30 presidential elections in 34 democracies between January 1st, 1919 and December 31st, 1945. **Figure 1** shows the distribution of regime types across the globe. 26 states featured a parliamentary regime (light grey), two a semi-presidential form of government (black), and four were presidential (dark grey).⁴ Geographically, the majority of democratic states were situated in Europe (25), while the rest clustered in Latin America and the Caribbean (5), in North America (2), and in the Pacific (2).⁵

Figure 2 depicts the frequency of legislative and presidential elections per decade.⁶ The declining number of elections tracks the breakdown of democracy in many European states and the conquest of surviving democracies by Nazi

⁴Parliamentary regimes feature no popular presidential elections. In semi-presidential regimes, the president is head of state but not head of the government. In presidential regimes, the president is both, head of state and head of government. Only Ireland changed its democratic regime type from parliamentary to semi-presidential when adopting a new constitution in 1937.

⁵The sample includes elections from Austria, Belgium, Czechoslovakia, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Iceland, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, San Marino, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, United Kingdom, Yugoslavia, Argentina, Chile, Colombia, Cuba, Uruguay, United States of America, Canada, Australia, and New Zealand.

⁶We omit 14 elections in 1919 from the graph.

Figure 1. Regime types across the world. First election per country depicted.

Figure 2. Democratic elections per decade, 1920-1945.

Germany. Notably, the steeper decline in legislative compared to presidential elections contrasts with the greater instability of presidential systems in the post-World War II period³⁰. Most likely, the pattern results from the clustering of presidential regimes outside Europe, and not from an inherent vulnerability to breakdown that parliamentary systems experienced during the period (see Figure 1).

Legislative elections

Most of the information in the DES data focuses on legislative elections. The included variables provide different classifications of electoral families, electoral rules, their application and combination within or across different levels of aggregation or electoral tiers, the number and average size of districts, and the resulting number of parties at each election. Figure 3 displays the distribution of legislative electoral families per decade. During the interwar period, electoral rules that translate votes proportionally into seats were roughly twice as common as majoritarian systems which award seats to the candidate(s) with the highest vote total(s) in a district. Combinations of proportional and majoritarian rules, so-called mixed systems, were uncommon during the interwar period.

Within the the broad electoral families, list PR systems were the most popular proportional rule with the D'Hondt divisor as the most common way to allocate votes into seats (59% of all PR elections). The remaining PR elections employed various quota systems, such as the Hare (17.27%), Hagenbach-Bischoff (15.83%), or Droop quota (7.19%). Single-member district pluralities or first-past-the-post elections constituted the preferred choice within the majoritarian electoral family (54.69%).

Two democracies used electoral systems that have not been used by any other state in national elections during the time period covered by any previous DES data release (1946-2020), and thus enter the DES data for the first time. Germany used the *fixed quota* system that distributed one seat for 60,000 votes^{31, 73-81}. Unlike most quota systems, which fix the number of parliamentary seats and determine the quota after counting the votes, the fixed quota system reverts this relationship. It sets the quota first and then determines the number of parliamentary seats. This practise led to an ever larger parliament as Germany's population and electoral participation grew. The size of the German Reichstag swelled from 459 deputies in 1920 to 647 members after the final election in March 1933. The second unique system, the *cumulative vote*, was employed in Chile until 1921³². It is similar in all but one respect to the majoritarian *block vote* system, in which voters have as many votes as there are seats in multi-member districts. However, voters can award more than one vote to a candidate under the cumulative vote.

Next to detailed information on legislative electoral rules, the DES data also provide insight into the consequences of these rules in the form of party system size figures. Figure 4 presents box plots of the effective number of electoral (enep) and parliamentary parties (enpp) across electoral families (top) and within families over time (bottom).⁷ In line with

⁷The effective number of parties measure summarizes the number of parties after an election by weighting each parties influence by its size. The weights in the electoral parties measure are vote shares, while the weights in the parliamentary party index are seat shares: $1/\sum_i^n s_i^2$, where s captures vote or seat shares and n is the number of parties.

Figure 3. Legislative families per decade, 1920-1945.

Figure 4. Party system size by electoral system family, 1919-1945.

theoretical predictions³³, majoritarian systems are associated with the smallest number of parties while PR systems are most permissive. From 1920 to 1940, the effective number of parties in PR systems decreases more steeply than in majoritarian systems (bottom panels). In part, this may be a selection effect where countries with more parties were more likely to fail. For example, four of the five democracies with the highest (*enep*) scores failed in the interwar period.⁸

Presidential elections

Presidential elections constitute just over 12% of all elections in the DES, 1919–1945 data. As shown in Figure 1 presidential regimes clustered in the Americas. European democracies were overwhelmingly of parliamentary types with semi-presidential exceptions in Finland, Germany, and Ireland after 1937. This low share contrasts markedly with the post-World War II period, when more than a quarter of all elections were presidential^{1,3}.

Mirroring the early post-World War II decades, the electoral college was the most common electoral system used in presidential elections during the interwar period, closely followed by plurality elections (see Figure 5). Absolute majority

systems and the alternative vote, that was only used in Ireland, were employed in less than 20% of all presidential elections.

Finally, we do not find any notable association between presidential electoral rules and the number of candidates. Whereas plurality systems are associated with a smaller and less variable number of presidential candidates relative to absolute majority systems in the 20th and 21st centuries^{3,34,35}, we find virtually no differences between electoral rules in the period 1919–1945. This null finding may be explained by the small number of elections observed during the period that does not result in sufficient variation. Moreover, the relatively young age of many democracies implies that candidates and voters had little time to learn about the mechanical and strategic effects of electoral rules.

Conclusion

In this data note, we described an update to the Democratic Electoral Systems (DES) data that extends the coverage to the period 1919–1945. Recently, concerns about the quality and survival of contemporary European and other long-established democracies are on the rise. Our new data can help answer questions about the association of parliamentary and presidential institutions as well as party system fragmentation on one hand, and the fate of democracies in another troubled period on the other. The DES 1919–1945 data might also be of use to scholars interested in the origins of electoral rules or long-term institutional legacies.

⁸These are Latvia, Estonia, Yugoslavia, and Germany. Czechoslovakia is the fifth country that we classify as having survived until the German occupation began.

Figure 5. Presidential electoral rules, 1919–1945.

Data availability

All figures and reported statistics can be replicated with R scripts contained in the dataverse. The authors ran the scripts on R version 4.3.1 (“Beagle Scouts”) and used the R packages *colorspace*³⁶, *cshapes*³⁷, and *ggplot2*³⁸.

Underlying data

Harvard Dataverse: Replication Data for: Introducing the Democratic Electoral Systems data, 1919–1945. <https://doi.org/10.7910/DVN/FWLXHM>¹⁸

This project contains the following underlying data:

- Electoral rules data: “es-1919-1945-231204.csv”
- Electoral results data: “es-1919-1945-results-231204.csv”
- Codebook: “es-1919-1945_codebook.pdf”
- Summary file: “readme.txt”

Data are available under the terms of the [Creative Commons Zero “No rights reserved” data waiver](#) (CC0 1.0 Public domain dedication).

Replication files

To replicate the figures in this study unpack the zip archive and

- R replication file: “data-es_interwar-master-231204.R”
- R replication file for Figure 1: “des_figure_regimetype.R”
- R replication file for Figure 2: “des_figure_elecdec.R”
- R replication file for Figure 3: “des_figure_elecdec.R”
- R replication file for Figures 4, 4a & 4b: “des_figure_enep_enpp.R”
- R replication file for Figure 5: “des_figure_preselecrule.R”

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The article „Introducing the Democratic Electoral Systems data, 1919-1945“, presents the most recent addition to the Democratic Electoral Systems around the world data. As the authors pointed out it encompasses the period from 1919 to 1945 and consists of 243 legislative lower house and presidential elections in 34 interwar democracies. The structure of the article is standard, consisting of an introduction, a description of the materials and methods, a substantial part, and a conclusion. The introduction is well structured and determines the framework and focus of the article. The methodology is described step-by-step, it is relevant for the goal of the study and is reproducible. The inclusion of regime types along with the electoral systems (and their sub-types) provides more options for analysis. The application of different conceptual frameworks to define democracy is another benefit for the users.

Substantially, the new addition to the DES dataset has a wide range of benefits for scholars and for all interested in the elections. The historical background is rather significant in the explanation of the contemporary state in a given national context, tracing the origins of transformations. Of particular importance is the collection of information for a historical period, which enables researchers to expand the range of analyses. Thanks to the addition to the database, it is now possible to compare the period before and after the Second World War, institutional transformations (in particular electoral legislation), and changes in societies. It is possible to examine the dynamics in a country's electoral rules from 1919 to the present by relating them to the dynamics in society. Alongside, associations between the structure of parliaments determined by the electoral rules and the decisions of states regarding the Second World War events might be identified. The above-mentioned are only part of the huge potential that the new database provides. In summary, current challenges cannot be fully understood without knowledge of the historical context, and DES 1919-1945 provides this opportunity to have accessible data on processes regarding the elections in contemporary democracies.

The submitted article can be indexed as is, both structurally and substantively. However, concerning the DES, I would like to make a suggestion. Some of the countries that do not appear in the database are democracies nowadays. It seems to me that following the evolution of their

electoral rules would contribute to a better understanding of the processes of democratization. Thus, if DES can be supplemented with more European countries although if not defined as democratic in the examined period, it will have a greater contribution to the comparative politics.

Is the rationale for creating the dataset(s) clearly described?

Yes

Are the protocols appropriate and is the work technically sound?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and materials provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

Are the datasets clearly presented in a useable and accessible format?

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Elections and electoral systems, comparative politics, political culture

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard.

Reviewer Report 10 June 2024

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Pedro Riera

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This is a much-needed article (dataset) on electoral systems in democratic countries in the interwar period. The authors have managed to compile an immense quantity of reliable and useful data that I expect to be widely employed by comparativists of all over the world in the coming years. For this main reason, I support indexing of the article. Having said that, I am listing in the next paragraphs a battery of ideas that, in my view, could improve the dataset and the resulting article.

1. My main concern about the article is that electoral systems per se should play a bigger role in it. Let me offer a couple of examples:
 1. Figure 1 displays information on regime types across the world. However, a similar graph with information on electoral system in use in each country does not exist. Electoral systems are the main object of the article and, as such, they should occupy a more prominent position when offering descriptive information.
 2. The article starts by very briefly explaining the main elements of the new dataset (i.e.,

electoral rules, consequences of electoral rules, democracy indices and ID variables). However, I was missing some extra focus on the electoral rules variables. Which ones are included in the article? One can imagine that these are going to be the same that appear in the “sequel”, the widely acclaimed Bormann et al.’s “Democratic Electoral Systems around the world, 1946-2020” dataset, but this needs to be explicitly said. On top of that, I have always considered the omission of an “electoral thresholds” variable in the original dataset as one its main mistakes. The reader wonders if this is also the case here and, if so, why the authors have not included information on this important element of democratic electoral systems.

2. Elections as unit of analysis. In the previous *Electoral Studies* articles, the authors use as unit of analysis the election rather than the country. This sometimes can result misleading because the number of elections a country holds depends, among others, on the constitutional inter-election period. In order to be sure that the latter is not entirely responsible for this effect, I suggest that the authors include a new variable in the dataset that captures the duration of the constitutional inter-election period.
3. Dubious theoretical claims:
 1. In page 5, the article argues that the steeper decline of the number of elections in PR countries is due to the geographical clustering of these countries in Europe rather than the type of system of government in place in these countries. However, the reader wonders how the geographical clustering of parliamentary systems in Europe can lead to this result. What is the (theoretical) mechanism linking these two variables (that is, geography and democratic survival)? I am aware of several ideas in this regard, the existence of domino/diffusion effects being the most prominent ones, but these points need to be made clearer in the article.
 2. In page 9, when talking about the effects of formulas in presidential elections, the authors allude to the “relatively young age of many democracies” to justify the existence of null effects in this regard. However, these effects do exist when examining the role of formulas in legislative elections (see previous pages). How can it be this discrepancy whether democracies are of relatively the same age?
4. Small points (page 6):
 1. When talking about how uncommon mixed systems were in the interwar period, provide examples (for example, Denmark).
 2. Why not including a figure about frequency of types of PR electoral formulas?

Is the rationale for creating the dataset(s) clearly described?

Yes

Are the protocols appropriate and is the work technically sound?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and materials provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

Are the datasets clearly presented in a useable and accessible format?

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Comparative politics, electoral systems, voting behaviour.

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Reviewer Report 31 May 2024

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The Democratic Electoral Systems (DES) dataset is an important addition to the existing scholarship on the electoral systems. The dataset includes a wide-range of information on 243 legislative lower house and presidential elections in 34 interwar democracies. The merit of the dataset stems from several factors. First, the paper covers a highly unique period in world history, i.e., the interwar years. Not only did this era witness the emergence and the spread of the most destructive political ideologies historically, but it also manifested the fragility of the so-called “established democracies” under non-democratic parties and leaders – even if they assumed power for a short period of time. Second, the dataset provides valuable insights into the trajectory of global electoral system changes, forming a foundational basis for future electoral engineering practices. Third, the dataset bridges a wide range of datasets through multiple identification variables. This allows researchers to make comparisons across different datasets and select the most suitable dataset for strengthening the empirical analysis. Fourth, the interdisciplinary nature of the DES dataset allows for the verification of proposed arguments against other aspects of electoral politics.

Despite these merits, some deficiencies should be stated. To begin with, first-hand sources are crucial for historical analysis, as few scholars possess sufficient resources to re-evaluate this period. This means that most scholars will possibly adopt the findings of this research without detailed investigation. From this perspective, the fact that some of the languages of the countries analyzed are not spoken by the research assistants may limit the reliability of the findings. Second, in which respect the DES dataset improves the understanding of the diffusion of electoral rules across Europe and the Americas is unclear. Historically, most of the colonized countries adopted the electoral systems of their imperial rulers. It remains to be seen whether such kind of diffusion can be mentioned for democracies as well. Third, additional information on how many elections are classified as “democratic” based on this reductionist account of the “democracy-dictatorship” classification would be beneficial. As widely noted, a binary classification overlooks the increasing prevalence of regimes that fall between these extremes. Finally, I am not fully convinced whether using the sub-title “democratic electoral systems” is conceptually appropriate. If we mention “democratic electoral systems,” then are there also “authoritarian” electoral systems or even

“totalitarian” ones? How do they look like? Imagine an electoral authoritarian regime with little or no ethnic and religious pluralism. If this country adopts an electoral system that maximizes descriptive representation of the society, can we call the electoral system “democratic”?

Is the rationale for creating the dataset(s) clearly described?

Yes

Are the protocols appropriate and is the work technically sound?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and materials provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

Are the datasets clearly presented in a useable and accessible format?

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: comparative politics

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard.
